

Synthesis and Biological Studies on some Spiro Schiff Base Derivatives

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Cycloaddition reactions of thioglycollic acid, monochloroacetyl chloride and diazomethane to Schiff bases afforded thiazolidinone, β -lactam and triazolidine derivatives respectively. These compounds have been tested against some bacterial and fungal strains.

Our interest in the synthesis of new systems having potential antibacterial activity¹⁻³ prompted us to explore the possibility of utilising some Schiff bases³⁻⁶ as substrates for the synthesis of new thiazolidine, β -lactam and triazolidine derivatives.

Cycloaddition of thioglycollic acid to the previously prepared Schiff bases (1)³ proceeded smoothly in boiling benzene to afford thiazolidinone derivatives (2a-f). The structures of compounds were confirmed by analysis, ir and nmr spectral data.

When the Schiff bases (1) were allowed to react with chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of triethylamine in dioxane⁷, they afforded the mono-substituted- β -lactam derivatives (3a-d) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M. p. °C	Yield %
2a	140	52
b	100-105	77
c	117	35
d	115	97
e	120	52
f	110	17
3a	110	60
b	130	9
c	185	35
d	155-160	35
4a	290	15
b	115	54
c	145	46
d	170	62
e	185	38
f	165	31
8	110	78
9a	141	84
b	134	65
c	171	76
d	149	71
e	156	59
f	161	64
10	180	72
11a	141	68
b	153	65
c	168	78
d	123	72
e	168	69
f	172	66
12	132	79
13a	161	83
b	174	64
c	162	69
d	151	66
e	139	63
f	146	71

*All compounds showed satisfactory elemental analyses.

The reaction of the Schiff bases (1) with CH_2N_2 gave the triazolidine derivatives (4a-f) (Table 1). The spiro Schiff base (5) was prepared by condensation of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (6) with 2-aminothiazole (7) in presence of a base catalyst.

The thiazolidinone derivative (8) was obtained by the cycloaddition reaction of 5 with thioglycolic acid in boiling benzene. Their structures were confirmed by elemental and spectral analyses. Condensation of the methyl group of the pyrazole moiety with benzaldehyde and its *p*-nitro, *p*-hydroxy, *o*-hydroxy, *p*-methoxy and 4-*N,N*-dimethylamino derivatives, afforded the styryl derivatives (9a-f) respectively, as proved by their elemental and spectral analyses. The β -lactam derivative (10) was prepared from 5 upon treatment with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine in dioxane. Similar condensation of 10 with benzaldehyde and its derivatives afforded the styryl compounds (11a-f). Finally the reaction of 5 with CH_2N_2 afforded the triazolidine compound (12).

The styryl derivatives (9a-f) were prepared by the condensation of 8 with benzaldehyde and its derivatives.

9, 11, 13a ; R = H b ; R = *p*-NO₂
 c ; R = *p*-OH d ; R = *o*-OH
 e ; R = *p*-OMe f ; R = *p*-NMe₂

The compounds of types 2, 3, 4, 9, 11 and 13 in ethylene glycol were tested *in vitro* against a number of bacteria and fungi by using filter paper disc method⁸ at 25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration. Many compounds showed high to moderate antibacterial activity as compared to standard antibiotic ampicillin. However, from the data it was difficult to find out a definite structure-activity relationship.

Experimental

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on an Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer. All melting points are uncorrected. The starting Schiff bases (1) were prepared according to the literature methods³⁻⁶.

The thiazolidinones (2a-f): An equimolecular mixture of the Schiff bases (0.01 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) was refluxed for 20 h. The reaction mixture was then evaporated to one-third under reduced pressure and allowed to stand at room temperature. In most cases the thiazolidinone was separated with addition of ice-water on the triturated residue and the product was washed with water (Table 1): $\nu_{\max}$ 1 698–1 690 cm^{-1} (C=O); **2e** nmr δ (DMSO- d_6) 6.8 (13H, ArH), 4.2 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{S}-$), 3.0 (3H, s, $\text{CH}_3\text{C}=\text{N}$) and 1.2–1.9 (4H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$).

β -Lactam derivatives (3a-d). General procedure: To a well-stirred solution of the Schiff bases (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) in dry dioxane (100 ml), was added chloroacetyl chloride (0.02 mol) dropwise at room temperature. The mixture was then stirred for additional 9 h and left at room temperature for 3 days. The precipitate of triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off and washed thoroughly with dioxane. The filtrate was evaporated to one-third of its original volume, cooled and ice-water was added. The residue was washed with water and dried: $\nu_{\max}$ 1 760 (β -lactam C=O) and 1 230 cm^{-1} (C=N); **3a** δ (DMSO- d_6) 8.6–6.5 (m, ArH), 3.7 (2H, s, CH_2), 3.3 (1H, s, CHCl), 2.8 (3H, s, CH_2 and CH) and 2.0 (3H, s, $\text{CH}_3\text{C}=\text{N}$).

The triazolidines (4a-f): A solution of the Schiff bases (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added to an ethereal diazomethane solution (obtained from 3 g nitrosomethyl urea) and the mixture was left in refrigerator for 10 days. The products were separated: $\nu_{\max}$ 1 530 (N–N) and 1 330 cm^{-1} (C–N); **4c** δ (DMSO- d_6) 6.7–7.5 (m, ArH), 5.6 (2H, s, N- CH_2), 3.3 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_2\text{O}$), 3.0 (3H, s, CH_3CN) and 2.8 (6H, s, N(CH_3) $_2$).

The Schiff base (5): A mixture of pyrazolone (4.3 g, 1 mol) and 2-aminothiazole (2.5 g, 1 mol)

in ethanol (20 ml) and few drops of piperidine was refluxed for 25 h. The hot reaction mixture was then poured on ice-water with stirring and left overnight. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from methanol as brown crystals, m.p. 195° (Found: C, 61.21; H, 4.87; N, 21.64; S, 12.18. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{S}$ calcd. for: C, 60.94; H, 4.69; N, 21.87; S, 12.53%); δ (CDCl_3) 1.82 (2H, s, CH_2), 3.11 (3H, s, $\text{CH}_3\text{C}=\text{N}$), 5.62 (2H, m, thiazole protons) and 6.86 (5H, ArH).

The benzaldehyde thiazolidinones (9a-f): A mixture of thiazolidinone **8** (0.3 g, 1 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.1 ml, 1 mol), ethanol (20 ml) and a few drops of piperidine as catalyst was refluxed for 15 h. The hot mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and left to stand until the products were precipitated. The yield and physical data are presented in Table 1: $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 670 cm^{-1} ; δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.7 (2H, s, CH_2), 4.26 (2H, s, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{S}$), 5.76 (2H, m, thiazole protons), 6.31 (1H, d, J 16.5 Hz, vinylic), 6.86 (1H, d, J 16.5 Hz, vinylic), 6.92–7.63 (10H, m, ArH). Similarly compound **11a-f** and **8a-f** were prepared by using appropriate starting materials.

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